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Research Article

DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF ORAL FLOATABLE IN-SITU GEL FOR INVASIVE FUNGAL INFECTION***¹Vazir Ashfaq Ahmed, ²Pooja H V, ³Mishba Nikhath, ⁴Sanjana S**
^{1,2,3,4} Ikon Pharmacy College, Bidadi.**Abstract:**

In the present study in-situ oral floatable gelling system of Posaconazole was successfully formulated by using different concentrations of gellan gum and pectin. Total eleven formulations were prepared with variable concentration of gellan gum and pectin. After performing the evaluation tests of prepared formulations, it can be summarized that Batch F9 was selected as best formulation, because it shows good release property of drug from the gel, having sufficient gel strength, shows optimum pH required for sol-gel conversion, and it also exhibit the acceptable result of other parameters. The release pattern of the optimized formulation (F9) was best fitted to a first order. The mechanism of the drug release was non-Fickian (super case II) transport. Non-Fickian (super case II) transport mechanism for releasing a drug associated with stresses and state-transition in hydrophilic glassy polymers, which swell in water or biological fluids. This term also includes polymer disentanglement and erosion. In-situ forming polymeric formulations drug delivery system is in a sol form before administration in the body, but once administered, it undergoes gelation in-situ to form a gel. The findings showed that the oral floatable in-situ gel offers a better sustained property compared to a conventional dosage form.

Keywords: Posaconazole, gellan gum, oral floatable gelling system.

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INTRODUCTION:

The drugs having a narrow absorption window in the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) when administered by the oral route are often limited by poor bioavailability due to incomplete drug release and short residence time at the site of absorption. Novel drug delivery systems, such as gastroretentive systems, have been developed in the form of floating systems, mucoadhesive systems, high-density systems, and expandable systems, as they provide controlled delivery of drugs with prolonged gastric residence times. Liquid orals are more prone to low bioavailability because they are rapidly eliminated from the stomach, as they undergo faster transit from the stomach to the duodenum. The problems of immediate release and short gastrointestinal residence of liquids are eliminated by formulating as oral *in situ* gels as they provide the best means to overcome these problems. The *in situ* gel dosage form is a liquid before administration and after it comes in contact with gastric contents due to one or more mechanisms gets converted to gel which floats on gastric contents. This achieves increased residence as well as sustained release. This approach is useful for the systemic as well as local effects of drugs administered¹.

The primary requirement of a successful controlled release product focuses on increasing patient compliance, which the *in situ* gels offer. Sustained and prolonged release of the drug, good stability and biocompatibility characteristics make the *in situ* gel dosage forms very reliable. Biodegradable and water-soluble polymers for the *in situ* gel formulations can make them more acceptable and excellent drug delivery systems. *In-situ* drug delivery provides a great potential for development of liquid orals for their sustained drug release. This floating *in-situ* gel approach is suitable for drugs having narrow absorption window in stomach or drugs showing local effect in stomach^{2,3}. Fungal infections kill more than 1.5 million people per year, which is similar to the mortality due to tuberculosis and about three-times more than malaria⁴.

Candidemia is one of the leading causes of blood-stream infections with mortality rate more than 30% whereas *Aspergillus* can affect more than 45% of susceptible host. Zygomycosis is common among diabetics all around the globe, including India. Mortality associated with invasive fungal infections among patients hospitalized in ICUs has reached to 67%⁵.

The presence of fungal elements either as mould or yeast in deep tissues of biopsy that is confirmed on culture and histo-pathological examination can be described as an Invasive Fungal infection (IFI).

Invasive fungal infections can involve any part of the body and are common in immune compromised patients, which usually result in high mortality. Among the fungi that have potential to cause IFI's include Yeasts (*Candida* spp, *Cryptococcus* spp) and moulds (*Aspergillus* spp, *Fusarium* spp, *Scedosporium prolificans*, *Mucor*, *Rhizopus* and *Rhizomucor Absidia*). Fungi have evolved as a major global health problem. This could be attributed to the immunosuppression either because of infections (AIDS) or cancer and metabolic disorders like diabetes⁶.

There are about 100,000 fungal species, of which only 300 species are known to cause animal or human infection. *Candida* spp is an opportunistic fungus that, being a normal flora of humans, can be responsible for significant infections from superficial skin and nail infections to urinary tract infections and candidaemia. *Candida* spp have been able to form biofilms, described as microbial adherence to either biotic or abiotic surfaces, forming a polymer matrix which becomes a substrate on which microbes grow. This ability makes *Candida* spp a potential cause of nosocomial infections. Long-term broad-spectrum antimicrobial therapy, cancer chemotherapy, presence of an indwelling catheter or other medical devices, extremes of age, and other biological factors also predispose individuals to IFI's⁷.

Posaconazole is an oral triazole with a useful spectrum of activity against many fungal pathogens of concern in patients at risk for the development of IFIs. Posaconazole is only available in oral formulation, and therapeutic drug monitoring may provide value due to variable absorption and serum concentrations. posaconazole has increased coverage spectrums relative to fluconazole and is generally less toxic than amphotericin products. Studies of IFI-associated mortality with amphotericin B, fluconazole, or itraconazole are associated with a high rate of infusion reactions and nephrotoxicity. In addition, fungi resistant to amphotericin B, such as *Aspergillus terreus*, have emerged as important human pathogens. fluconazole has no activity against certain *Candida* species and most filamentous fungi, while itraconazole has multiple drug-drug interactions and variable bioavailability. In the new antifungal drugs like as voriconazole and echinocandins, have emerged. Both are well tolerated and active against most *Candida* and *Aspergillus* species. However, both also lack activity against notable causes of post-transplantation IFIs, including the zygomycetes and *Fusarium* species⁸.

Reports have documented the emergence of echinocandin resistance during treatment of candidemia. So a drug with a broad spectrum of

activity against both yeasts and filamentous fungi, as well as a high barrier to the development of resistance, may provide a useful therapeutic option. posaconazole possesses an *in vitro* spectrum of activity comparable with amphotericin B, an oral formulation, and a low risk of adverse events⁹.

The proposed work aims to formulate and evaluate an oral floatable *in-situ* gel of posaconazole, to achieve greater therapeutic efficacy by ensuring increased residence as well as sustained release using natural biodegradable polymers.

Materials And Methods:

Posaconazole was obtained as a gift sample from SunPharma, East Sikkim, India. GellanGum was

procured from Applied Bio Sciences. (Mumbai). Pectin was procured from Sardan gums and Chemical Inds (Delhi). Calcium Chloride, Calcium Carbonate, Sodium citrate were obtained from the chemical provider.

Preparation of Drug-Loaded *In-situ* gel: ¹⁰

Polymer solutions were prepared by stirring the gellan gum and pectin in de-ionized water by heating to 60°C. After cooling below 40°C, various concentrations of CaCO₃, CaCl₂, Sodium citrate, and the drug will be dispersed/dissolved one by one under continuous stirring. The formulations were filled in amber-coloured bottles, which were tightly capped. The composition of the prepared *in situ* gel formulations is shown in Table 1

Table 1: Composition of the prepared *in-situ* gelling formulations:

Batch Code	Drug	Gellan Gum	Pectin	CaCO ₃	CaCl ₂	Sodium Citrate	De-ionized Water
F1	2.5%	0.5%	1.0%	2.0%	0.15%	0.45%	Up to100 ml
F2	2.5%	1.0%	1.0%	2.0%	0.15%	0.45%	Up to100 ml
F3	2.5%	1.5%	1.0%	2.0%	0.15%	0.45%	Up to100 ml
F4	2.5%	0.8%	1.5%	1.5%	0.15%	0.45%	Up to100 ml
F5	2.5%	1.2%	1.5%	1.5%	0.15%	0.45%	Up to100 ml
F6	2.5%	0.8%	2.0%	1.5%	0.15%	0.45%	Up to100 ml
F7	2.5%	1.2%	2.0%	1.5%	0.15%	0.45%	Up to100 ml
F8	2.5%	0.8%	1.5%	2.0%	0.15%	0.45%	Up to100 ml
F9	2.5%	1.2%	1.5%	2.0%	0.15%	0.45%	Up to100 ml
F10	2.5%	0.8%	2.0%	2.0%	0.15%	0.45%	Up to100 ml
F11	2.5%	1.2%	2.0%	2.0%	0.15%	0.45%	Up to100 ml

Evaluation of Prepared *In-situ* Gel

The prepared *in-situ* gel was evaluated for its Physical appearance /Clarity, Viscosity, pH, Gel-strength, *in-vitro* gelling capacity, *In-vitro* buoyancy, floating time determination, Drug content, *in-vitro* release study, *In-vitro* drug release kinetics, and Stability.

Physical Appearance / Clarity: ¹¹⁻¹²

The developed formulations were inspected visually for clarity under a black and white background. Clarity of the formulations was found to be satisfactory at both room temperature and refrigerated conditions. Physical Appearance / Clarity data of the prepared *in-situ* Gel are shown in Table 2.

Viscosity Measurement: ^{11, 13}

This is an important parameter for the *in-situ* gels, to be evaluated. The viscosity values were measured with the Brookfield digital viscometer

(Model No. DV-II *Pro*). 100 ml of each formulation was taken in a beaker and maintained at room temperature. Then, the spindle number 2 was allowed to rotate in the sample solution containing the beaker. For the determination of viscosity, spindle no. 2 was used in the plate and cone viscometer. Viscosities were determined at different shear rates from 00 to 100 rpm at room temperature. Viscosity data of the prepared *in-situ* Gel are shown in Table 3.

pH Determination of the Gel: ¹²

Ten millilitres of each formulation were put into a beaker and inspected for viscosity by using a digital pH meter (Model No. dot 461, Manufactured by Dot Tech.) at room temperature. The measurements of pH were done in triplicate, and the Average values are given in Table 4.

Gel Strength Determination: ¹⁴

A 50 g prepared gel was placed in a 100 mL

graduated cylinder. A probe on the gel and a weight of 15 g was placed on the probe. The probe was allowed to penetrate a fixed of 5cm(30ml). The time it took for the distance was recorded A sample of 50 ml of the gel was put in a 100 ml graduated cylinder containing gelation solution having a temperature of 37°C. A weight of 35 g was placed onto the gelled solution. The gel strength was determined by the time in seconds required for the weight to penetrate 5 cm into the gel. Results are shown in Table 5.

***In-vitro* gelling capacity:** ^{10, 12, 15-16}

To evaluate the formulations for their *in-vitro* gelling capacity by visual method, solutions of *in situ* gel-forming drug delivery system were prepared. The *in-vitro* gelling capacity of prepared formulations was measured by placing 5 ml of the gelation solution (0.1N HCl, pH 1.2) in a 15 ml borosilicate glass test tube and maintaining it at 37±1°C temperature. One ml of formulation solution was added with the help of a pipette. The formulation was slowly transferred from the pipette to the surface of the fluid in the test tube. As the solution comes in contact with gelation solution, it is immediately converted into a stiff gel-like structure. The gelling capacity of the solution was evaluated based on the stiffness of the formed gel and the period for which the formed gel remains as such. The *in-vitro* gelling capacity was graded in three categories on the basis of gelation time and the time period for which the formed gel remains. (+) Gels after a few minutes, dispersed rapidly (++) Conversion of gel immediately remains for 12 h (+++). Conversion of gel immediately remains for more than 12 h. *In-vitro* gelling capacities of the prepared *in-situ* gel are shown in Table 6.

***In-vitro* buoyancy test:** ^{12, 15, 17}

The study was determined by using the USP dissolution apparatus II, having 500 ml of 0.1 N HCl solution (pH 1.2). The medium temperature was maintained at 37±20 °C. 10 ml of the prepared *in-situ* gel formulations was drawn up using a disposable syringe and placed into the petri dish (4.5 cm internal diameter), and finally petri dish containing the formulation was kept in the dissolution vessel containing medium without much disturbance. The time the formulation takes to emerge on the medium surface (floating lag time) was noted and reported in Table 7.

Floating time determination: ^{10, 12, 15-17}

Floating time was determined using USP dissolution apparatus II, having 500 ml of 0.1 N HCl solution (pH 1.2). The medium temperature was maintained at 37±20°C. 10 ml prepared *in-situ* gel formulations were drawn up using a disposable syringe and placed into the Petridis (4.5 cm internal diameter), and finally Petridis containing the

formulation was kept in the dissolution vessel containing medium without much disturbance. The time in minutes the formulation constantly floats on the dissolution medium surface (Duration of floating) from the time of gel formation was noted and reported in Table 7.

Drug Content Determination: ^{13, 15, 17}

Accurately, 10 ml of *in-situ* gel formulations was measured and transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask. To this, 50-70 ml of 0.1(N) HCl was added and shaken on a mechanical shaker for 30 min, followed by sonication for 15 min. Complete dispersion of contents was ensured, visually and filtered using a 0.45 µm membrane filter. From this solution, 10 ml of the sample was withdrawn and diluted to 100 ml with 0.1(N) HCl. Contents of the drug were determined spectrophotometrically at 285 nm using double-beam UV-Visible spectrophotometer. Drug content data of the prepared *in-situ* gel are shown in Table 8

***In-vitro* Drug Release Study:** ^{16,17}

The following procedure was followed to determine the *in-vitro* dissolution rate for the prepared formulations. The release of the drug from the formulations was determined using a dissolution test apparatus USP Type II with a paddle stirrer at 50 rpm for 8 h. The slow speed prevented breaking of the gelled formulation and ensured a low level of agitation. As dissolution medium 900 ml of 0.1N HCl (pH 1.2) solution was used and temperature was maintained at 37 ± 0.2 °C. 10 ml of sample formulation was withdrawn by using a disposable syringe at every one-hour interval (predetermined time interval is one hour); the needle was then wiped clean and the excess sample removed from the needle end. The sample was then gently transferred into a petri dish, which was then immersed in the dissolution medium without much disturbance. At each pre-determined time interval, a precisely measured sample of the dissolution medium was pipetted out and replenished with fresh medium. Drug concentration in the aliquot was analyzed spectrophotometrically after filtering through 0.45 µ nylon filters. Each study was conducted in triplicate. *In-vitro* drug release data of the prepared *in-situ* gel are shown in Table 9, 10, and Figure 1, 2.

Stability Study: ¹⁵

The prepared formulations were packed in amber-colored bottles, which were tightly plugged with cotton and capped were stored for three months, and the stability of the *in-situ* gel formulation of Posaconazole was monitored up to 3 months at Controlled temperature (40 ± 20 °C) and controlled humidity (75 ± 2 % RH) conditions. Periodically (initial, 1, 2, and 3 months) samples were removed and evaluated for pH, viscosity, drug content, *in-*

vitro gelling capacity, floating lag time, total floating time, and *in-vitro* drug release study. And

the data that has been found are reported in Table 11.

Result And Discussion:

Table 9: Physical Appearance / Clarity of Prepared *in-situ* Gels:

Sl. No.	Batch Code	Physical appearance / Clarity
1.	F1	Off-white colored clear solution was obtained.
2.	F2	Off-white colored clear solution was obtained.
3.	F3	Off-white colored clear solution was obtained.
4.	F4	White colored clear solution was obtained.
5.	F5	White colored clear solution was obtained.
6.	F6	White colored clear solution was obtained.
7.	F7	White colored clear solution was obtained.
8.	F8	Pale Yellow colored clear solution was obtained.
9.	F9	Pale Yellow colored clear solution was obtained.
10.	F10	Pale Yellow colored clear solution was obtained.
11.	F11	Pale Yellow colored clear solution was obtained.

The prepared *in-situ* gel was inspected visually for clarity. All the formulation was found as a clear solution. Among eleven formulations the colour of the three formulations (F1, F2, F3) was Off-white, four was white coloured (F4- F7), and another four was Pale Yellow coloured. Results are shown in table 9.

Viscosity Measurement:

The viscosity of the prepared *in-situ* gels at both liquid and gel form, which was found are given below

Table 3: Viscosity Measurement of Prepared *in-situ* Gels:

Sl. No.	Batch Code	Viscosity (cp) Mean \pm SD*	
		Liquid form	Gel form
1.	F1	245 \pm 0.10	280 \pm 0.20
2.	F2	252 \pm 0.15	289 \pm 0.20
3.	F3	259 \pm 0.10	296 \pm 0.35
4.	F4	263 \pm 0.20	307 \pm 0.20
5.	F5	271 \pm 0.15	314 \pm 0.15
6.	F6	282 \pm 0.10	326 \pm 0.10
7.	F7	245 \pm 0.25	282 \pm 0.20
8.	F8	248 \pm 0.20	285 \pm 0.15
9.	F9	278 \pm 0.10	322 \pm 0.10
10.	F10	300 \pm 0.10	342 \pm 0.10
11.	F11	315 \pm 0.15	367 \pm 0.20

Standard deviation (SD), n=3

The viscosity of the formulations increased with an increase in polymer concentration. This phenomenon is a consequence of increasing chain interaction with an increase in polymer concentration. Calcium carbonate, which is the source of cations, increased the viscosity of the formulation. This change in viscosity is due to the proportional increase in the amount of dispersed calcium carbonate. The viscosity of the prepared formulations was found in the range of 245 to 315 cp. The viscosity of the optimized formulation (F9) was 278 cp. Results are shown in Table 10.

pH Determination:Table 4: pH Determination of Prepared *in-situ* Gels:

Sl. No.	Batch Code	pH Mean \pm SD*
1.	F1	7.1 \pm 0.23
2.	F2	7.09 \pm 0.12
3.	F3	7.15 \pm 0.1
4.	F4	7.08 \pm 0.02
5.	F5	7.13 \pm 0.05
6.	F6	7.17 \pm 0.1
7.	F7	6.90 \pm 0.7
8.	F8	7.15 \pm 0.5
9.	F9	7.2 \pm 0.01
10.	F10	7.07 \pm 0.1
11.	F11	7.15 \pm 0.10

Standard deviation (SD), n=3

Prepared formulations were evaluated for pH studies and found to be between 7.07 - 7.2. The pH of the optimized formulation (F9) was found to be 7.2.

Gel Strength Determination:Table 5: Gel Strength Determination of Prepared *in-situ* Gels:

Sl. No.	Batch Code	Gel Strength (Second) Mean \pm SD*
1.	F1	06.10 \pm 0.03
2.	F2	07.20 \pm 0.08
3.	F3	11.35 \pm 0.12
4.	F4	08.45 \pm 0.08
5.	F5	12.06 \pm 0.14
6.	F6	11.52 \pm 0.11
7.	F7	13.12 \pm 0.23
8.	F8	11.45 \pm 0.24
9.	F9	13.58 \pm 0.01
10.	F10	12.23 \pm 0.16
11.	F11	14.12 \pm 0.15

***In-vitro* gelling capacity Determination:**Table 6: *In-vitro* gelling capacity Determination of Prepared *in-situ* Gels:

Sl. No.	Batch Code	Gelling Capacity
1.	F1	++
2.	F2	++
3.	F3	++
4.	F4	++
5.	F5	++
6.	F6	++
7.	F7	++
8.	F8	++
9.	F9	++
10.	F10	+++
11.	F11	+++

The Gelation Strength of the prepared *in-situ* gel, the result was found in the range of 06.10 Seconds to 14.12 seconds. From the result, it can be said that, with increasing polymer concentration, gelation strength was also increased. The Gelation Strength of the optimized formulation (F9) was found to be 13.58 seconds.

The *in-situ* formed gel should preserve its integrity without dissolving or eroding for a prolonged

period to facilitate the sustained release of drugs locally. F1 to F9 formulations form gel immediately and remain for 12 hours. Formulations F10 and F11 form gel immediately and remain for more than 12 h. Low concentration of polymer is responsible for a weak cross-linked three-dimensional network of gel, which might be that is the reason for the degradation of gel after a few hours. Like that high concentration of gellan gum and pectin forms high high-stiff gel.

***In-vitro* buoyancy:**

Table 7: *In-vitro* buoyancy, Floating time of prepared *in-situ* Gels:

Sl. No.	Batch Code	<i>In-vitro</i> buoyancy (Sec.) Mean \pm SD*	Floating time (h.)
1.	F1	29 \pm 0.34	>12
2.	F2	35 \pm 0.23	>12
3.	F3	39 \pm 0.09	>12
4.	F4	53 \pm 0.10	>12
5.	F5	65 \pm 0.12	>12
6.	F6	48 \pm 0.22	>12
7.	F7	68 \pm 0.16	>12
8.	F8	31 \pm 0.09	>12
9.	F9	36 \pm 0.03	>12
10.	F10	178 \pm 0.13	>12
11.	F11	205 \pm 0.21	>12

The buoyancy lag time varied with the formulation variables. Formulation F1 exhibited the least buoyancy lag time (29 s) while formulation F11 exhibited the highest lag time (205 s). The decrease in the buoyancy lag time of a formulation F1 might be due to escape of CO₂ air bubbles from the gelling network because of low concentration of polymer. The *in-vitro* buoyancy time of the optimized formulation (F9) was found to be 36 Seconds. All the formulations (F1 to F11) were shown the total floating lag time more than 12 hr. The possible reason behind that, combination of pectin and gellan gum form stiff gelling system after contact with HCl.

Drug Content Determination:

Table 8: Drug Content Determination of Prepared *in-situ* Gels:

Sl. No.	Batch Code	Drug Content (%) Mean \pm SD*
1.	F1	99.62 \pm 0.07
2.	F2	99.54 \pm 0.22
3.	F3	98.05 \pm 0.13
4.	F4	98.45 \pm 0.05
5.	F5	98.86 \pm 0.08
6.	F6	99.23 \pm 0.1
7.	F7	99.69 \pm 0.12
8.	F8	97.85 \pm 0.11
9.	F9	98.34 \pm 0.06
10.	F10	98.89 \pm 0.17
11.	F11	98.81 \pm 0.10

The Drug content of all (F1-F11) formulations is given in the table no 8 . It ranges between 97.85% - 99.69%. The drug content of the optimized formulation (F9) was found to be 98.34%.

In-vitro Drug Release Study:Table 9: *In-vitro* Drug Release Study of Prepared *in-situ* Gel (F1 – F6)

Sl. No.	Time (hrs.)	Cumulative % Drug Release (CPR) Mean \pm SD*					
		F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	1	65.00 \pm 0.02	62.00 \pm 0.4	59.00 \pm 0.08	51.00 \pm 0.50	44.50 \pm 0.2	57.00 \pm 0.5
3	2	67.00 \pm 0.5	65.10 \pm 0.15	64.20 \pm 0.03	72.20 \pm 0.02	61.40 \pm 0.2	62.30 \pm 0.3
4	3	68.90 \pm 0.1	66.30 \pm 0.3	65.60 \pm 0.1	77.50 \pm 0.15	69.20 \pm 0.1	66.90 \pm 0.1
5	4	70.20 \pm 0.2	69.60 \pm 0.1	68.50 \pm 0.2	79.70 \pm 0.30	78.70 \pm 0.05	68.70 \pm 0.02
6	5	78.60 \pm 0.1	75.20 \pm 0.3	73.20 \pm 0.2	80.60 \pm 0.10	84.40 \pm 0.02	70.60 \pm 0.01
7	6	84.50 \pm 0.5	83.90 \pm 0.02	80.80 \pm 0.4	81.30 \pm 0.20	96.50 \pm 0.02	76.50 \pm 0.2
8	7	91.40 \pm 0.3	89.50 \pm 0.03	90.20 \pm 0.1	84.60 \pm 0.10	98.00 \pm 0.23	78.80 \pm 0.3
9	8	99.70 \pm 0.4	95.10 \pm 0.1	97.70 \pm 0.2	88.60 \pm 0.20	99.40 \pm 0.04	81.00 \pm 0.5

Figure 1: *In-vitro* Drug Release Curve of Prepared *in-situ* Gel (F1 – F6)Table 10: *In-vitro* Drug Release Study of Prepared *in-situ* Gel (F7 – F11)

Sl. No.	Time (h.)	Cumulative % Drug Release (CPR) Mean \pm SD*				
		F7	F8	F9	F10	F11
1	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	1	49.00 \pm 0.02	50.00 \pm 0.4	54.00 \pm 0.08	47.00 \pm 0.5	39.50 \pm 0.2
3	2	55.00 \pm 0.5	58.10 \pm 0.15	63.20 \pm 0.03	52.20 \pm 0.02	46.40 \pm 0.2
4	3	62.90 \pm 0.1	64.30 \pm 0.3	67.60 \pm 0.1	59.50 \pm 0.15	52.20 \pm 0.1
5	4	73.20 \pm 0.2	71.60 \pm 0.1	75.50 \pm 0.2	66.7 \pm 0.3	64.70 \pm 0.05
6	5	75.60 \pm 0.1	76.20 \pm 0.3	82.20 \pm 0.2	70.60 \pm 0.1	73.40 \pm 0.02
7	6	78.50 \pm 0.5	84.90 \pm 0.02	87.80 \pm 0.4	77.30 \pm 0.2	76.50 \pm 0.02
8	7	79.40 \pm 0.3	92.50 \pm 0.03	94.20 \pm 0.1	82.6 \pm 0.1	81.00 \pm 0.23
9	8	82.70 \pm 0.4	98.10 \pm 0.1	99.70 \pm 0.2	85.6 \pm 0.2	84.40 \pm 0.04

Figure 2: *In-vitro* Drug Release Curve of Prepared *in-situ* Gel (F7 – F11)

The *in-vitro* drug release of the stomach-specific oral *in-situ* floating gel was carried out in 0.1N HCl from 0 to 8 h by USP type-II apparatus, and the values are shown in the respective table mentioned in the result portion. The plot of % Cumulative drug release v/s time (hrs) was plotted. An *in-vitro* drug release study was conducted on the formulations for a period of 8 h during which the highest drug release of $99.70 \pm 0.2\%$ ($n=3$) was observed with formulation F9, and the least drug release of $81.00 \pm 0.5\%$ with F6 during the 8-h dissolution study.

As the concentration of gellan gum and pectin used

in the formulation was increased from low to high, a decrease in the amount of drug release was observed. The drug release from the formulations with higher gellan gum and pectin were slower compared to formulations with medium and low concentrations of gellan gum and pectin.

Stability Testing:

After storing, periodically (initially, 1, 2, and 3 months), the selected formulation was removed and evaluated for pH, viscosity, drug content, *in-vitro* gelling capacity, *in-vitro* buoyancy, total floating time, and *in-vitro* drug release study.

Table 11: Stability Testing Data

Evaluation for pH				
Formulation	Initial	After 1 month at $40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ & $75\% \text{RH} \pm 5\% \text{RH}$	After 2 months at $40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ & $75\% \text{RH} \pm 5\% \text{RH}$	After 3 months at $40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ & $75\% \text{RH} \pm 5\% \text{RH}$
F9	7.2	7.2	7.2	7.2
Evaluation for Viscosity				
Formulation	Initial	After 1 month at $40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ & $75\% \text{RH} \pm 5\% \text{RH}$	After 2 months at $40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ & $75\% \text{RH} \pm 5\% \text{RH}$	After 3 months at $40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ & $75\% \text{RH} \pm 5\% \text{RH}$
F9	278	276	276	276
Evaluation for Drug Content				
Formulation	Initial	After 1 month at $40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ & $75\% \text{RH} \pm 5\% \text{RH}$	After 2 month at $40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ & $75\% \text{RH} \pm 5\% \text{RH}$	After 3 month at $40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ & $75\% \text{RH} \pm 5\% \text{RH}$
F9	98.34	98.30	98.11	97.87
Evaluation for <i>in-vitro</i> gelling capacity				
Formulation	Initial	After 1 month at $40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ & $75\% \text{RH} \pm 5\% \text{RH}$	After 2 months at $40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ & $75\% \text{RH} \pm 5\% \text{RH}$	After 3 months at $40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ & $75\% \text{RH} \pm 5\% \text{RH}$

F9	++	++	++	++
Evaluation for <i>in-vitro</i> buoyancy				
Formulation	Initial	After 1 month at 40°C±2°C & 75%RH ± 5%RH	After 2 months at 40°C±2°C & 75%RH ± 5%RH	After 3 months at 40°C±2°C & 75%RH ± 5%RH
F9	36 Sec.	36 Sec.	37 Sec.	37 Sec.
Evaluation for total floating time				
Formulation	Initial	After 1 month at 40°C±2°C & 75%RH ± 5%RH	After 2 months at 40°C±2°C & 75%RH ± 5%RH	After 3 months at 40°C±2°C & 75%RH ± 5%RH
F9	>12 h.	>12 h.	>12 h.	>12 h..
Evaluation for <i>in-vitro</i> drug release study (F9)				
Time	Initial	After 1 month at 40°C±2°C & 75% RH ± 5%RH	After 2 months at 40°C±2°C & 75% RH ± 5%RH	After 3 months at 40°C±2°C & 75%RH ± 5% RH
0	0	0	0	0
1	54.00±0.08	53.76±0.06	53.55 ±0.23	53.50±0.06
2	63.20±0.03	62.92±0.12	62.87 ±0.13	62.86±0.09
3	67.60 ±0.1	67.43 ±0.14	67.40 ±0.1	67.38 ±0.12
4	75.50 ±0.2	75.10 ±0.02	75.03 ±0.12	75.00 ±0.03
5	82.20 ±0.2	81.93 ±0.11	81.89 ±0.11	81.88 ±0.05
6	87.80 ±0.4	87.34 ±0.07	87.31 ±0.03	87.28 ±0.01
7	94.20 ±0.1	94.12 ±0.45	94.10 ±0.21	94.05 ±0.1
8	99.70 ±0.2	99.60 ±0.08	99.58 ±0.04	99.55 ±0.09

The optimized Formulation F9 was evaluated for stability studies, which were stored at 40°C±2°C & 75%RH±5%RH for 3 months and were tested at 1-month intervals for their pH, viscosity, drug content, *in-vitro* gelling capacity, *in-vitro* buoyancy, total floating time, and *in-vitro* drug release study. All the result of the formulations was found to be within the permissible limits.

SUMMARY:

Oral Posaconazole is indicated for the treatment of serious infections caused by susceptible strains of *Candida* or *Cryptococcus neoformans*. It can also be used for the treatment of chromomycosis (chromoblastomycosis), if susceptible strains cause the infection. Minor infections such as candidal cystitis may be treated with Posaconazole alone. In conventional dosage forms, it undergoes first-pass metabolism of 40% where the oral bioavailability (100%) was reduced to 60%. The patient's compliance may be improved due to the decrease in frequency of drug administration by this prepared dosage form.

In the present study, we propose to develop a novel *in situ* gel system for sustained drug delivery of Posaconazole for rapid onset in Mycosis, using natural biodegradable polymers. The identification

characteristics of a drug, like solubility, melting point, λ_{max} were used to find out the purity of the drug. All the parameters observed were satisfactory and were within the prescribed official limits.

In this study, gellan gum and pectin were used as smart polymers, which are the most widely used biodegradable natural polymers for controlled release formulations, that undergo sol-gel transition once administered in response to pH stimuli. The drug polymer compatibility was confirmed by FTIR studies. The results obtained by FTIR studies revealed that there was no chemical interaction between the pure drug and polymer.

In the present study, a total of eleven formulations were prepared with variable concentrations of gellan gum and pectin. The entire batch contains both of the polymers; only the concentration was different in each batch. After performing the evaluation tests of prepared formulations, it can be summarized that batch F9 was selected as the best formulation, because it shows good release property of the drug from the gel, has sufficient gel strength, shows optimum pH required for sol-gel conversion, and it also exhibits acceptable results of other parameters. The release pattern of this

optimized formulation was best fitted to a first order. The mechanism of the drug release was non-Fickian (super case II) transport.

REFERENCE:

1. Patil SG, Shahi SR, Dandale JJ. In-situ gel: a gastro-retentive drug delivery system, Int J Pharm Sci. 2025;3(1):278-93.
2. Rajdeep Gupta, Ragini Singh Bundela "Formulation and evaluation of gastroretentive *in situ* gelling system of saxagliptin". Curr Res Pharma Sci 2025;15(1): 8-13.
3. Puri G. Ashutosh, Sandeep C et al. Formulation and evaluation of in-situ gel for periodontal disease. Asian J Pharma Res Devel. 2025;13(3): 48-58
4. Firacative C. Invasive fungal disease in humans: are we aware of the real impact Mem Inst Oswaldo Cruz, Rio de Janeiro 2020; (115): e200430
5. Ravikant, Kaur T, Gupte S, et al. A review on emerging fungal infections and their significance J Bacteriol Mycol 2015;1(2):39-41
6. Ramana KV, Kandi S, Kumar VB. Invasive fungal infections: a comprehensive review Am J Infect Dis Microbiol 2013;1(4):64-9
7. Lai CC, Tan CK. Current challenges in the management of invasive fungal infections J Infect Chemother 2008; 14:77-85
8. Collins CD, Smith JA, Kaul DR. Prophylaxis of invasive fungal infections: a review of the use of posaconazole. Clin Med Ther 2009; 1:1399-408
9. Page AV, Liles WC. Posaconazole: A new agent for the prevention and management of severe, refractory or invasive fungal infections. Can J Infect Dis Med Microbiol 2008;19(4):297-305.
10. Rathod H, Patel V, Moin M, *In-situ* gel as a novel approach of gastro retentive drug delivery. IJPLS 2010; 1(8):440-447
11. Pandya K, Agrawal, Dashora A, et al. Formulation and evaluation of oral floatable *in-situ* gel of ranitidine hydrochloride. J Drug Del & Therapeutics 2013; 3(3): 90-97
12. Wamorkar V, Varma MM, Manjunath SY, Formulation and evaluation of stomach specific *in-situ* gel of metoclopramide using natural, bio-Degradable polymers. Int J Res Pharm Biomedical Sci 2011; 2(1): 193-201.
13. Badgujar SD, Sontakke MA, Narute DR, et al. Formulation and evaluation of sumatriptan succinate nasal in-situ gel using fulvic acid as novel permeation enhancer. Int J Pharm. Res. and Dev. 2010; 2(8): 47-52
14. Vora V, Basu B, Formulation and characterization of novel floating *in-situ* gelling system for controlled delivery of ramipril. Int J Drug Del 2013; 5: 43-55.
15. Thomas LM. Formulation and evaluation of floating oral *in-situ* gel of metronidazole. Int J Pharm Pharm Sci 6(10): 265-269
16. Panwar AS, Sharma M, Formulation and evaluation of floating stomach specific *in-situ* gel of nizatidine. Int J Pharm & Biological Archives 2014; 5(1): 115-123.
17. Xu H, Shi M, Liu Y, Jiang J, Ma T. A novel *in situ* gel formulation of ranitidine for oral sustained delivery. Biomol Ther 2014 22(2):161-5.